

The Design of Children's Picture Book from the Tales of Amphawa Fireflies

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Abstract : The research objective aims to search information about storytelling and fable associated with fireflies in Amphawa community, in order to design and create a story book which is appropriate for the interests of children in early childhood. This book should help building the development of learning about the natural environment, imagination, and creativity among children, which then, brings about the promotion of the development, conservation and dissemination of cultural values and uniqueness of the Amphawa community. The population used in this study were 30 students in early childhood aged between 6-8 years-old, grade 1-3 from the Demonstration School of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. The method used for this study was purposive sampling and the research conducted by the query and analysis of data from both the document and the narrative field tales and fable associated with the fireflies of Amphawa community. Then, using the results to synthesize and create a conceptual design in a form of 8 visual images which were later applied to 1 illustrated children's book and presented to the experts to evaluate and test this media.

Keywords : children's illustrated book, fireflies, Amphawa

Conference Title : ICCVAD 2014 : International Conference on Communication, Visual Arts and Design

Conference Location : Istanbul, Turkey

Conference Dates : May 22-23, 2014